

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

No. 28

• Tunisia

Detection of toxic *Alexandrium catenella* (Whedon & Kofoid) Balech in clam production zone of North Lake and Channel, Tunisia

Fig. 2. *Alexandrium catenella*: (a) microphotograph with phase contrast; (b) microphotograph with epifluorescence, ventral view; (c) dorsal view; (d) Po, 1' and Sa; (e) sulcal plates; (f) apical plates of epitheca; (g) Hypotheca.

A dozen species of *Alexandrium* have been identified in the Bay of Tunis, of which two are toxic, *A. tamarense* and *A. minutum* [1]. During our monitoring of the production zones

of bivalve molluscs in northern Tunisia, *A. catenella* was detected for the first time in the Tunis Channel in August 1997. This species seems to be well adapted to the Mediterranean, and may

have been introduced with ballast water [2]. In addition, these are the kinds of ecosystem, estuarine and lagoonal, which are most vulnerable to invasions [2].

(Cont'd on p.2)

SEED: A new EU-US collaboration on HABs

The word SEED is not an acronym or abbreviation; it directly refers to seed as produced by plants. However, the indication 'SEED' refers to a new project entitled *Life cycle transformations among HAB species, and the environmental and physiological factors that regulate them*, for which we do not

want an acronym.

The project is funded by the Global Change and Ecosystems Programme of the European Commission and the U.S. National Science Foundation. SEED started in March 2005 and will continue for three years. SEED is endorsed by the Global Ecology and Oceanography

of Harmful Algal Blooms programme of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (GEOHAB) as a Targeted Research Project.

Two coordinators, a steering committee, and 12 partners make up the

(Cont'd on p.3)

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Fig. 1. Sampling stations in shellfish production area of North lake and Channel of Tunis.

In the Mediterranean, the first appearance of *A. catenella* dates from 1983 along the Catalan coast [3], and its distribution gradually extended along the northwest Mediterranean coast with recurrent blooms during the period 1997 to 1999 in the port of Barcelona, and with associated production of paralytic toxins [4]. Toxic episodes due to the presence of gonyautoxins and saxitoxins in L'étang de Thau are attributed to *A. tamarensis* with *A. catenella* also suspected [5]. The latter species has also been noted in Sardinian waters (Tyrrhenian Sea) [6].

The present report follows the annual pattern of this toxic species in the

North Lake and Channel of Tunisia (Fig. 1) where the main resources of the clam *Tapes decussatus* are concentrated. These two sites have been monitored for toxic planktonic microalgae since 1996 [7].

The North Lake of Tunis was earlier marked by the presence of recurrent 'green tides' of *Ulva lactuca*, and important ecological changes have occurred in the last dozen years following restoration works which were made in the period 1984 to 1988. In particular, there has been a net increase in macrophyte diversity, and marine phanerogams have appeared [8]. Among the toxic species mentioned in

the clam production zones in the North Lake and Channel, only species producing diarrhetic toxins, *Dinophysis* spp and *Prorocentrum lima*, have previously been detected [9, 10]. The navigation channel is strongly perturbed by anthropogenic pollution due to the existence of three ports, with a direct impact on the benthic macrofauna which may extend as far as the adjacent Gulf of Tunis [11]. A first appearance of red water due to a bloom of *Noctiluca scintillans* was recorded in March

(Cont'd from p. 1)

2003 along the southwest coast of the Gulf.

The characteristic morphology of *A. catenella* is shown in Fig. 2. These cells are solitary, and rarely seen in chains or pairs. Total length varies from 25 to 32.5 μm , and the transverse diameter from 19 to 32 μm . The epitheca is very fragile relative to the hypotheca, which sometimes lacks the pore at the level of plate Sp. This species is found at certain times of the year (March 2005) accompanied by *Scropsiella trochoidea* and *Gonyaulax spinifera*. Differentiation between these cells is made by means of epifluorescent microscopy after staining the cells with calcofluor.

Annual variations in the abundance of *A. catenella* above the critical level of 500 cells/L have rarely been found except in June in the Channel of Tunis, and in two periods, December and February to March, in the North Lake (Fig. 3). Estimated maximum concentrations are respectively 1300 cells/L in the Channel (T2) in March 2005 and in June 2004, and 1000 cells/L in the North Lake (T1 Chikly).

It is still too early to state that this species is increasing in abundance in the clam production zones in the North Lake and Channel of Tunis. Our future studies should allow us to follow the evolution of *A. catenella* which has been detected since its first appearance.

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Fig. 3. Concentrations of *A. catenella* (cells/L) in the clam production zone in the North Lake and Channel of Tunis (February 2004 - March 2005).

(Cont'd from p. 1)

consortium of SEED and include scientists from 7 European countries and the USA.

SEED aims to understand to what extent environmental and physiological factors may influence the non-vegetative stages of the life cycles of harmful algal bloom (HAB) species, thereby contributing to the increase in harmful algal blooms (HAB) in European marine, fresh, and brackish waters. SEED will focus on the life histories of some of the most relevant HAB species in Europe.

The areas to be studied comprise the regions bordering coastal sites in the Western Mediterranean Sea, Atlantic Ocean, North Sea, Baltic Sea, and Swedish lakes. All of these regions have heavy anthropogenic influences: fisheries, urban development, aquaculture and tourism. All are subject to the frequent occurrence of HABs, with a variety of detrimental impacts including human intoxications, closure of shellfish farms, water discoloration causing a negative impact on tourism, etc.

The approach of SEED is comparative, ranging from species to ecosystem levels. Despite considerable phylogenetic distance, many morphological and physiological traits of HAB species are convergent and common.

The specific objectives are:

1. To characterize and quantify the different stages of the life cycle in a bloom development of selected HAB species in comparative environments.

2. To characterize the physiological mechanisms and tolerances underlying dormancy stages/cysts, spores and akinetes, their formation and germination for key HAB species.

3. To explore the mating interactions of non-toxic and toxic HAB species to better understand the nature of species invasions or dispersions and to evaluate the use of non-toxic strains as a possible mitigation strategy in HABs.

4. To quantify the flux of cells of key HAB species in different areas from and to the sediments.

5. To investigate the role of sedimentary dynamics in the preservation, accumulation and dispersion of dormant stages.

6. To explore methods to identify

From bottom to top and from left to right: Toni Jordi, Gotzon Basterretxea, Esther Garcés, Karin Rengefors, Donald Anderson, Mercedes Masó, Robin Raine, Jordi Camp, Sílvia Anglès, Jordi Solé, Kees van Lenning, Rosa Isabel Figueroa, Antonella Penna, Marina Montresor, Magda Vila, Kalle Olli, Nicolas Touzet, Deana Erdner, Santiago Fraga, Sanna Suikkanen, Isabel Bravo, Anke Kremp, Jane Lewis, Hartmut Barth, Marta Estrada, Mariagrazia Giacobbe, Elena Bertozzini, Cecilia Satta, Antonella Lugliè, Maria Laamanen, Carmen Hormigo, Dolors Blasco.

specific life cycle stages of key HAB species through molecular or immunological techniques.

7. To use the newly acquired knowledge in simple numerical models to verify the relevance of life history features and to develop or refine predictive and conceptual models of bloom dynamics for selected HAB species, taking into account life-history.

8. To determine the role of dormancy stages of HAB species in different environments in relationship to the expansion/increase of HABs. To formulate principles that explain similarities between ecosystems.

To facilitate the development of conceptual and numerical models of HAB dynamics, it is imperative to recognize common patterns of response among species. In recognition of this convergence and to carry out cost-effective research, SEED will take advantage of existing model species while keeping the main focus on an array of target HAB species, which range from marine to brackish to fresh water organisms, and cover a broad range of phylogenetic types (dinoflagellates, diatoms, raphidophytes, cyanobacteria).

New results will be used to elucidate and evaluate the role of life cycle processes, especially dormancy stages, in bloom dynamics. Furthermore, one aim of SEED is to integrate the acquired knowledge into the development of new model formulations. This improved

modelling will enhance prediction and support the development of new management and mitigation strategies for these species.

For further information on the project, visit our website: www.icm.csic.es/bio/seed/

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• Mexico

Ostreopsis siamensis (Dinophyceae) a new tycho planktonic record from Isabel Island National Park, Pacific Mexico

Fig. 1. Study area and sampling locations.

An early summer sampling programme was carried out from 18th May to 26th June 2004, around Isabel Island National Park (Fig. 1). Isabel Island is a major Pacific nesting site for seabirds, principally frigate birds, blue footed and yellow footed boobies, pelicans, swallows, sea gulls and brown footed boobies. Its origin is volcanic, dating back approximately 3.5 million years; it has been used as a temporary camp for fishermen in the area. The climate is tropical, with a long wet summer season (May to October) and a short dry winter season (November to April). The rainy season coincides with hurricanes and tropical storms in the zone. Diverse and abundant coral reef communities cover 4.93% of the island [1]. The study was done to describe the general phytoplankton community, and to document the distribution of toxic dinoflagellates. Until now, harmful algae have never been investigated in this island. We report for the first time the occurrence of the potentially toxic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis siamensis* Schmidt 1902, and its geographical distribution in the Mexican Pacific area.

Phytoplankton samples were collected during early summer at five sta-

tions in Isabel Island National Park. The samples containing *Ostreopsis siamensis* were obtained from surface net tows using a 62 μm pore size plankton net, towed by boat at a low speed for 4 minutes, very close to coral reef in shallow waters. The specimens were fixed immediately with 4% glutaraldehyde solution. Surface water temperature (25°C), salinity (35.3‰) and dissolved oxygen (6.15 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) were measured in-situ with an YSI model 85. Phytoplankton cells were identified using the Utermöhl technique and a phase-contrast microscope. Morphological details were observed through scanning electron microscopy (JEOL/OE jsm-6360).

The morphological characteristics of the organisms were in accord with the descriptions of Fukuyo [2] and Faust [3], which coincide in all plates of the

genus, the epithecal (Fig. 2a), the hypothecal (Fig. 2b), ventral zone (Fig. 2c) and both kind of pores (Fig. 2d). The shapes and dimensions of the Po plate are characteristic of each species and different from the other species as shown in Fig. 3. The dorso-ventral distance ranged from 88 to 129 ($\frac{1}{2}$ 101) μm and transdiameter from 65 to 90 ($\frac{1}{2}$ 78.4) μm . Our report confirms the presence of *O. siamensis* as part of the natural biota in this latitude. It is possible that Isabel Island waters generate favorable environmental conditions for the proliferation of benthic dinoflagellates, which are transported later by currents to the plankton zone (= tycho plankton). The species has often been reported as benthic, epiphytic, but is most frequently associated with sand and as an epiphyte on seaweeds [4]. Further analysis will outline the

Fig. 2. Thecal plates of *Ostreopsis siamensis*: a) Epitheca, b) Hypotheca, c) Ventral region, d) Small and large pores.

seasonal distribution, outbreak times, summer-winter survival and species succession in this fishery location, as well as its abundance. According to Faust [3] the ecology of *O. siamensis* is diverse; the type species was identified from plankton samples collected by Schmidt from the Gulf of Thailand. Some years later, the morphology of *O. siamensis* was reexamined by Fukuyo [2] based on specimens from Ryukyu Island in Japan. *O. siamensis* is also known from South Florida, Florida Keys, Puerto Rico, U.S. Virgin Islands, Hawaii, Guam and New Zealand [5, 6].

This species is known to be toxin producer. Nikajima *et al.* [7] were the first, followed by Yasumoto *et al.*, [8] and Holmes *et al.* [9] to indicate the presence of toxins produced by *O. siamensis* populations, which produces ostreocin D, an analog of palytoxin, one of the most potent marine toxins known. Palytoxin can accumulate in fish and crabs and is considered responsible for clupeotoxism, an illness linked to the eating of sediment-feeding fishes in Japan [6]. It is also thought to be the cause of the multiplicity of symptoms in the pathology of ciguatera [10]. The toxin affects first coral grazing fish, then piscivorous fish, notably groupers, and finally humans. Other organisms affected are snapper, mackerel, jack, goat fish, barracuda, parrot fish, and some gastropods [5]. Until now, no clinical case of ciguatera has been reported in the island by health authorities, but the high to moderate abundances of *Ostreopsis* cells observed raise the possibility that ostreocin or another kind of palytoxin, are responsible for different seafood poisoning (ciguatera, clupeotoxism, etc.). Strong coastal surface currents have been proposed as major players in the transport of cells to the island waters.

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Fig. 3. The morphology of the Po plates: a) *O. siamensis*, b) *O. ovata*.

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• Turkey

Toxic and harmful algal species in the Izmit Bay, Marmara Sea

During the last 40 years, nutrient concentrations have obviously increased in many estuaries and coastal waters in the world due to the influence of human activities [1, 2]. This problem of marine eutrophication has been highlighted in recent years by the occurrence of increasingly severe toxic phytoplankton blooms in many near-shore waters worldwide. Toxic phytoplankton blooms in the sea are of even greater concern than in freshwater ecosystems [3]. Red tides and other toxic and/or noxious algal blooms mainly due to progressive eutrophication from terrestrial inputs have been observed by reporters and Turkish scientists [4]. Balkis and Aktan [5] reviewed plankton studies in the Marmara Sea (except Izmit Bay) continuing since the 1990s [6-10, 11], leading to the identification of 11 toxic phytoplanktonic species.

Izmit Bay, located in the north-eastern part of the Marmara Sea is one of the most polluted areas in the Marmara Sea, and an important centre for Turkish industry. The bay has been receiving more than 300 industries' effluents together with untreated domestic waste waters from the small cities, and from Izmit which is the most populous city of the region. Pollution problems have gradually become more serious since 1960. Previous studies showed that the bay waters have become eutrophic [1,

12] and red tides due to *Prorocentrum* species, and fish mortalities, have been observed in some periods (unpublished data).

This paper focuses on the toxic and/or harmful phytoplanktonic and benthic microalgal species recorded in Izmit Bay. In March 1999 and September 2000, phytoplankton, epiphytic, and epipelagic algae were collected from sampling sites.

Fourteen toxic and harmful species; dinophytes *Ceratium furca* (Ehrenberg) Claparède & Lachmann, *Dinophysis acuminata* Claparède & Lachmann, *Dinophysis acuta* Ehrenberg, *Dinophysis caudata* Saville-Kent, *Dinophysis sacculus* Stein, *Gymnodinium sanguineum* Hirasaka, *Lingulodinium polyedrum* (Stein) Dodge, *Noctiluca scintillans* (Macartney) Kofoid & Swezy, *Phalacroma rotundatum* (Claparède & Lachmann) Kofoid & Michener, *Prorocentrum micans* Ehrenberg, *Prorocentrum minimum* Schiller; and diatoms *Pseudo-nitzschia delicatissima* (P.T. Cleve) Heiden in Heiden & Kolbe, *Pseudo-nitzschia* sp. (*Nitzschia seriata* (Hasle) were recorded in the bay. In addition to these species, *Prorocentrum lima* (Ehrenberg) Dodge was recorded as epipelagic and epiphytic (on *Bryopsis hypnoides* Lamour, *Codium fragile* (Sur) Hariot, *Cystoseira barbata* C. Agardh var. *barbata*, *Cymadocea*

nodosa (Uchria) Ascherson and *Zostera noltii* (Horneman)) in the littoral zone. *Prorocentrum lima* is a benthic dinoflagellate usually found attached to or associated with macrophytes, floating detritus, debris or other substrates and less commonly in plankton. These species were common in Izmit Bay, but toxic and noxious algal blooms were not recorded during the sampling period.

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• Mexico

First record of *Chattonella marina* in Bahía de la Paz, Gulf of California

Harmful algal blooms are common events in Bahía de La Paz, a coastal lagoon located on the southwest side of the Gulf of California [1]. A massive bloom of *Chattonella marina* was observed from April 24 to May 9, 2005 in Bahía de La Paz (Fig. 1). Live cells of *C. marina* were identified in unfixed

samples. For cell enumeration water samples were fixed using acid lugol (1%) and analyzed with the standard Utermöhl technique [2]. Fixed cells were deformed and shrank making it difficult to identify without observing live cells (Fig. 2). Cell densities fluctuated between 1.9 and 3.5 x 10⁶ cells L⁻¹.

Cysts of *C. marina* were not observed in these samples, which suggests that environmental conditions were good for this species. Sea surface temperature during the bloom was 22°C. During monitoring on May 4th at a different collection site, *C. marina* cells were also observed but in lower concentrations

Fig. 1. Collection site showing location and size of *Chattonella marina* bloom (shaded area) in Bahía de La Paz. * Indicates the site of additional sample.

which ranged from 11 to 23 x 10³ cells L⁻¹. As in other areas, different cell morphologies were observed (Fig. 2). However, in the samples collected on May 4th, round cells resembling temporary cysts were observed.

The presence of the ichthyotoxic phytoflagellates *C. marina*, *C. cf ovata*,

Fibrocapsa japonica, and *Heterosigma akashiwo* (Raphidophyceae) have been reported in various localities on the Mexican Pacific coast as well as in the Gulf of Mexico [3, 4, 5], including a previous bloom report on the east coast of the Gulf of California [6]. However this is the first report of a bloom of *C.*

marina for Bahía de La Paz. The highest abundances estimated for this event were an order of magnitude higher than previous reports [6].

Most marine Raphidophyceae are ichthyotoxin producers, and have caused severe fish mortalities with significant damage to the aquaculture economy in several countries. In Mexico loss of marine resources was associated with the presence of *C. marina* and *C. cf ovata* in Kun Kaak Bay, Sonora [6]. In Bahía de La Paz no fish or shellfish mortalities were observed, however the magnitude of this event is of special concern for fisheries and aquaculture activities in this area.

It is possible that these species have been undetected in most Mexican waters due to traditional methods used for sampling and preserving phytoplankton. Raphidophyceans like other flagellates, are very delicate, and deform or disintegrate in formalin solution; samples preserved with lugol have different morphology but can be recognized by a well-trained eye. We recommend that during the monitoring of harmful algae, non-preserved samples should be taken to observe the presence of delicate phytoplankton forms. During the bloom, clonal cultures were isolated. These will be used in the near future to confirm toxicity.

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Fig. 2. Light photomicrographs of *Chattonella marina* collected in Bahía de La Paz. Live cells (1-3), acid lugol fixed cells (4), and spherical cell showing flagella (3).

First report of *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii* in Italy

Fig. 1. *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii* (600x).

Abstract

Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii is a freshwater cyanobacterium of tropical origin, also found in temperate regions. It can produce toxins like cylindrospermopsin (CYN) and saxitoxins (STX, NEO). In 2004, it was detected in three Italian lakes (Albano Lake, Trasimeno Lake and Cedrino Lake). Two of the three examined cases were toxic to a liquid chromatography coupled with tandem spectrometry apparatus (LC-MS/MS), and analysis demonstrated the presence of cylindrospermopsin (CYN).

Formerly *C. raciborskii* blooms were detected in 1995 (Trasimeno Lake), in 2002 (Albano Lake) and in 2003 (Cedrino Lake), but in those cases no toxicity analysis were performed due to the lack of a standard toxin.

Introduction

Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii (Wolos.) Seenaya et Subba Raju (Fig. 1) is a cyanobacterium found principally in freshwaters, although it has been detected also in the Caspian Sea [1].

C. raciborskii is filamentous, variable in length and 1-5 mm wide. The extremities of its trichomes are sharp, due to the shape of the terminal heterocysts [2].

C. raciborskii releases, during senescence or as a consequence of envi-

ronmental stresses (such as thermal shocks or water purifying processes), a dangerous toxin, cylindrospermopsin, but saxitoxins (STX, NEO) can also be produced [3], the toxin affects the liver, kidneys, thymus and heart. Additionally, a carcinogenic potential can be observed *in vitro* [4].

The first episode of cylindrospermopsin human poisoning, caused by contaminated drinking water, was recorded in Palm Island (Australia) in November 1979, and led to an outbreak of hepatoenteritis [6].

C. raciborskii, originally known from central African and Australian lakes, is now to also recorded in temperate regions such as Germany [7], Portugal [8], and France [9].

Massive blooms of *C. raciborskii* were first noted in Italy in summer (June to September) 1995, in the lakes of Albano and Trasimeno. Moreover, from September to November 2003 trichomes of this species were observed in raw waters of a drinking water treatment plant in Sardinia (up to 15×10^6 cells L^{-1}), which treats water extracted from Cedrino Lake.

As the blooms of this cyanobacterium do not appear as floating scums and only slightly modify water colour, it is difficult for human eyes to spot the hidden danger. It is necessary to prevent access to

contaminated waters and to conduct steady and exhaustive controls on endangered waters, and to improve public awareness of this issue.

Methods

Samples were collected from Albano Lake (July 2004) and Trasimeno Lake (Sept 2004) in central Italy, and from Cedrino Lake (Oct 2004) in central Sardinia.

For toxin analyses, 1 L water surface samples were collected in the central areas of the three lakes.

The microscopic observations of phytoplankton were carried out on Lugol fixed samples, using an inverted microscope. Cell density was determined by the Utermöhl technique. For the chemical analysis 0.2 ml of the sample (water) was directly injected into a liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass-spectrometry apparatus (LC-MS/MS). Quantitation of cylindrospermopsin in samples was assessed by comparing its peak area resulting from the total ion current to that obtained by injecting a standard solution. The limit of quantification (LOQ) of the method was 0.22 ng/ml. The liquid chromatograph consisted of a Waters pump (Model 1525 μ , Milford, USA), inline filter (2 μ m pore size), Alltima 5- μ m C-18 guard (7.5 x 4.6 mm i.d.) and analytical (250 mm x 4.6 mm i.d.) columns (Alltech) and was interfaced to a Micromass 4 MICRO API, Waters. For fractionating the analytes, phase A was acetonitrile and phase B was water, both 10 mmol/L formic acid. The mobile phase gradient profile was as follows (t in min.): t_0 , A= 0%; t_8 , A= 16%; t_9 , A= 100%; t_{12} , A= 100%; t_{13} , A= 0%; t_{22} , A= 0%.

Results

The phytoplankton analysis revealed that the maximum density of *C. raciborskii* in Albano Lake (July 2004) was 6×10^6 cells L^{-1} , in Trasimeno Lake (Sept. 2004) was 9×10^6 cells L^{-1} , in Cedrino Lake (Oct. 2004) was 81×10^6 cells L^{-1} .

The chemical analysis revealed a concentration of cylindrospermopsin in

Albano Lake of 15 ng ml⁻¹, toxin trace in Trasimeno Lake (0.46 ng ml⁻¹) and no toxicity was found in Cedrino Lake.

Discussion

Cylindrospermopsin is an unusual alkaloid (m.w. 415 Da) and consists of a trycyclic guanidine moiety combined with hydroxymethyluracil [10]. Apart from liver toxicity, mutagenicity [11] was shown *in vitro* and evidence also exists for its carcinogenicity *in vivo* [12]. The LD₅₀ (i.p.) in mice is cells/kg 2,1 mg/kg over 24 h [13]. The occurrence of *C. raciborskii* on the three Italian lakes is correlated with a toxic presence of cylindrospermopsin only in two cases. The maximum density of *C. raciborskii* was found in the Cedrino Lake but the maximum toxin concentration was registered in Albano Lake: this demonstrates that wild populations of cyanobacteria species, catalogued as toxic, not necessarily or always, are implicated in toxin production.

Few years ago, the presence of *C. raciborskii* was revealed in Europe, only as far as Germany [6] Portugal [7], France [8] and now the presence in Italy is confirmed by observations over a ten-year period. The extending geographical distribution of this species could be linked to the migration of water birds

like gulls, as they are important agents of dispersal for many aquatic organisms, by carrying resistant forms within their intestinal tract. The dispersal of freshwater species not capable of active overland transport and lacking resistant forms, while not so well documented has largely been attributed to transport via external surfaces of birds [14]. Comparative studies on ecological conditions and on phylogenetic relations of European wild populations of *C. raciborskii* could help to explain their difference in toxin production, too.

Anyway, these data show for the first time that *C. raciborskii* can also be found in Italian water bodies, also for drinking use, and that monitoring this cyanobacterium and associated cylindrospermopsin is a real emergent necessity.

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IOC Training Course on Qualitative and Quantitative Determination of Algal Toxins, Germany, 22 February to 2 March 2005

The IOC-BMU-AWI-DZMB-FSU JENA Training Course on Qualitative

and Quantitative Determination of Algal Toxins was held at the Wattenmeerstation Sylt, AWI in List/Sylt, Germany from 22nd February to 2nd March 2005. The course was the first in a series of five cooperative training courses implemented by IOC and Forschungsinstitut Senckenberg (DZMB), Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena (FSU) und Stiftung Alfred-Wegener-Institut für Polar- und Meeresforschung in der Helmholtz-Gesellschaft (AWI). It was financed by IOC and Germany: Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit (BMU); Applied Biosystems Darmstadt and Mr J. Gosch, Gosch-Seafood Tourist Service GMBH, List/Sylt, supported the course.

The course was hosted at the Wattenmeerstation Sylt of AWI and or-

ganized by Dr. Malte Elbrächter (FIS) Germany and in cooperation with Dr. Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC, Paris, Prof. Dr. Allen Cembella, AWI-Bremerhaven, Germany and Prof. Bernd Luckas, FSU-Jena, Germany with his team. Applications arrived from 96 persons from 46 nations. Due to financial and space limitations only 12 participants originating from 11 countries could attend the training course.

The goal of the course was to provide participants with an overview of the state of the art of different analytical methods for qualitative and quantitative determination of phycotoxins. Lectures and demonstrations on all relevant toxins were performed, and the participants were encouraged to establish scientific collaboration.

Qualitative and quantitative determination of algal toxins using different analytical methods (HPLC with selec-

tive detection, HPLC/MS coupling and LC-MS) were made on samples of algae and mussels provided mainly by the participants. The laboratory experiments focused on the analysis of Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP), Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP), Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), and cyanobacterial toxins by application of chromatographic methods.

The next training course is planned for October 2006.

Marine and Freshwater Toxins Analysis First Joint Symposium and AOAC, Baiona, Spain, 11 - 14 April 05

Task Force Meeting was held April 11-14, 2005, in Baiona, Spain. The conference was convened under blue skies at the Hotel Talaso Atlantico just above the rugged coastline of the prolific mussel-producing Galicia region. The meeting was well attended by a global mix of academics, government regulators, seafood and analytical industries and industry associations. Over 120 participants pre-registered and over 150 attended in total.

The Minister of Fisheries of the Galician Government as well as the former Minister of Health of Galicia, who was instrumental to success in his supportive role working closely with the

University of Vigo since the first efforts to manage the threat of marine toxins in Galicia, opened the conference. Also present was the Vice Rector of Institutional Affairs. Symposium Chair Ana Gago Martinez, and Task Force Chair James Hungerford spoke briefly and next warm recollections were given by Jose Antonio Rodriguez Vasquez, chair of the Analytical and Food Chemistry Dept., University of Vigo, of exciting and productive collaborations of the University with visiting researchers from Japan and Canada. Other keynote presentations followed on the current state of marine biotoxin monitoring in Galicia and an overview and progress

report of the Marine and Freshwater Toxins Task Force.

Many excellent keynote and contributed presentations were given throughout the meeting. A unique aspect of the conference in Baiona was the integration of the Symposium and Task Force meetings, with the symposium presentations (72 total, 35 oral) preceding subgroup discussions in relevant toxin areas. This allowed for discussion of method applicability, current validation efforts, future directions, and a variety of other topics relating to toxin analysis methods and their validation. Discussion threads from the new AOAC on-line forums of the Task Force sup-

plemented these in-person subgroup meetings and discussion periods. Subgroup areas included in the Baiona program included assays for saxitoxins, LC methodology for saxitoxins and domoic acids, okadaic acids and azaspiracids, yessotoxins, and ciguatoxins. Benjamin Suarez-Isla, James Lawrence, Ana Gago Martinez, Aurelia Tubaro, and co-chair Robert Dickey (for ciguatoxin chair Richard Lewis) chaired these sessions. Two other areas discussed were cyanobacterial toxins and LC-MS methods for multiple toxin groups. These very active areas are new to the Task Force and will soon become formal subgroups when chairs are appointed this year.

Benjamin Suarez-Isla, the subgroup chair, led discussion of saxitoxin assays with the primary focus on an IAEA-funded initiative to validate a receptor-binding assay (RBA) for the saxitoxins using radiolabeled saxitoxin. He presented results of a Single Laboratory Validation (SLV) study submitted by Fran Van Dolah, the RBA assay project leader. Participants also suggested pursuit of receptor binding assays using alternative (non radioactive) labels. James Lawrence led subgroup discussion on LC methods for saxitoxins and domoic acids. A positive vote by the Task Force last year has moved a pre-column oxidation LC method for the saxitoxins into review by AOAC for official method status. This method is now in the final stages of First Action approval following minor revisions. Still, post-column methods for saxitoxins also remain an area of interest, with recent advances made by Japanese and Canadian research groups.

Several presentations on the cyanobacterial toxins were also given and the availability of toxin test kits was discussed, building on responses obtained following a request for this information in the on-line forum. Participants shared some of their experiences with the kits and additional kits were brought into the discussion, as was the need for cyanobacterial reference standards. The ciguatoxin subgroup session began with a proposal put forward in the ciguatoxin on-line forum by Robert Dickey to establish a reference collection of ciguatoxic fish tissues. The fish

tissues would cover a range of ciguatoxicity and tissue origin and would be characterized by a combination of cytotoxicity assay and LC-MS methods. Practical issues including stability, storage requirements, costs, and issues regarding tissue sample transport were discussed.

Okadaic acids, their congeners and also azaspiracids were discussed in a subgroup chaired by Ana Gago Martinez and this addressed a range of topics. These included both PP2A assay marketed in Japan based on enzyme inhibition and a Biosense method based on competitive binding assay, also using PP2A. Also the relative merits of these two functional assays versus LC-MS-MS became the subject of a lively discussion. At the conclusion of this session was a statement that validation of both classes of methods, those based on assays and also LC-MS, should be pursued without competition between the two. At this stage each group, consisting of the LC-MS enthusiasts and those working on functional assays like PP2A, should reach a consensus on extraction conditions, which congeners to include, etc. Then validation plans should continue to move ahead as the overall process can be time consuming. The toxin sessions concluded with presentations on yessotoxin toxicology and yessotoxin detection methods followed by a yessotoxin subgroup meeting chaired by Aurelia Tubaro of Italy. Existing methodology and validation plans were discussed from the standpoint of single laboratory validation, and the issue of which YTX forms to include in methods was also discussed. The symposium was concluded with presentations by European government, industry, and industry association stakeholders. In these talks the need for validated methods was stressed, as was the need to make them stakeholder-friendly.

Comments from those who attended this four-day combined symposium and Task Force meeting were very positive and discussions and plans made at the conference rekindled hopes in the validated of additional methods.

The on-line forums will be used to review and carry forward what was discussed in Spain and to engage in fur-

ther discussions both the Baiona participants and all interested in development, validation and application of methods for the toxins. As another step in our continuous path towards validated methods, a meeting will be held June 22-24, 2005 in Seattle, Washington, USA, in connection with the Pacific Northwest Regional AOAC Meeting. In Orlando, Florida, USA, a full Task Force meeting consisting of several toxin subgroups, will meet as part of our second symposium-Task Force conference at the AOAC Annual Meeting September 11-15, 2005. Two symposia, including a full day devoted to *Marine and Freshwater Toxins Analysis: Quality Methods for Public Health and International Trade*, and also a half-day session to honor Wiley Award winner Mike Quilliam, will precede these Task Force meetings. As with all our meetings, we encourage both researchers and stakeholders (and potential stakeholders) to attend.

SEPTEMBER 2006

12th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HARMFUL ALGAE

September 4-8, 2006. Copenhagen, Denmark.

Call for submission of abstracts and registration form: February 1, 2006.

Deadlines:

- Abstracts reception: May 1, 2006
- Early registration: June 1, 2006
- Late registration: July 15, 2006

Further information can be found at: www.issaha.org.

Future events

DECEMBER 2005

GEOHAB: OPEN SCIENCE MEETING. HABS AND STRATIFICATION

December 5-8, 2005. UNESCO Headquarters, Paris, France.

The conference topics include:

- Physical processes relevant to stratification
- Maintenance of HAB populations in thin layers
- Selection of assemblages by different turbulent regimes
- Changes in small scale physical properties caused by the phytoplankton community
- Implications for sampling, monitoring and operational oceanography
- Detection systems

Important dates:

- Abstract deadline: October 1, 2005.
- Early registration deadline: November 1, 2005.

Further information can be found at: www.geohab.info.

Harmful Algae News

Previous issues of HAN and newsletters of the IOC HAB Programme can be downloaded at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

Requests for subscription

Subscription to HAN is made by sending a request with a complete address to Ms V. Bonnet (v.bonnet@unesco.org).

ISSHA

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

ISSHA President's Corner

News from the 11th HAB meeting in Capetown, South Africa

Announcement of election of officers for the next 2 years include Patricia Tester as President, Karen Steidinger as acting past President, Gustaff Hallegraeff and Beatriz Reguera as Vice President, Tracy Villareal as Secretary and Nina Lundholm as Treasurer.

ISSHA's emphasis during the next two years will be to update the web site. Tracy Villareal is working with Stephen Bates, former ISSHA Secretary, to accomplish this. Take a look at www.issaha.org and see how that is coming. ISSHA is committed to increasing its visibility and will be featured in a poster during the Third Symposium on Harmful Algae in the U.S., 2-7 October 2005 (www.visitasilomar.com). Also, ISSHA is a co-host for the summer ASLO (American Society of Limnology and Oceanography) meeting in Victoria 6-9 June 2006. Increasing our membership base is key to our success as an organization and we welcome new members, especially, student members and say thank you to our life-

time members for their strong show of support.

Maureen Keller Awards

Five Maureen Keller Student Awards were presented by ISSHA at the 11th Conference on Harmful Algae held in Cape Town, South Africa. Please join me in congratulating these young researchers for their excellent oral presentations and posters. Also, thanks go to the other students who presented 67 posters and 19 oral presentations and whose work helped spark many discussions during the meeting. The 32 judges who generously agreed to help evaluate the efforts of this diverse body of student work were recognized individually at the banquet. However, I would like to say again how much I appreciate their assistance to the ISSHA awards committee.

Though no biography is present, mention should also be given to the fifth awardee, M-L Chateau-Degat for her presentation on Neurological Signs of Ciguatera Disease.

Pat Tester, ISSHA President.

Members of the ISSHA Council during the IV General Assembly of the Society (Cape Town, South Africa, 18 Nov. 2004). From left to right: Beatriz Reguera, Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Don Anderson, Adriana Zingone, Ojvind Moestrup, Edna Granéli, Allan Cembella, Max Taylor and Pat Tester.

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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